

**D8.4 DATA
MANAGEMENT
PLAN AND
ETHICS REPORT**

WP8, T8.4
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ABSTRACT

This deliverable presents the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the SPOON project. This formal document provides a framework and overview for how data will be handled during and after the SPOON project. Initially submitted as D8.4 in month 6 (M6), the second version will be updated to D8.5 in month 20 (M20), and the final DMP for the project, scheduled for submission in month 38 (M38). The objective of this DMP is to detail what data will be generated by the project. It also specifies the standards and methodologies for data collection and management, as well as strategies to ensure that data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR principles).

The DMP will be made publicly available on the project website. All partners are expected to review and adhere to both current and final versions of the DMP, along with their associated processes and requirements.

DISCLAIMER

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	SPOON
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- *PU = Public
- SEN= sensitive

D8.4 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN AND ETHICS REPORT

CHANGE HISTORY / REVIEW TABLE

v	Date	Beneficiary and description	Author
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D1	09/05/2025	Internal reviewers provided feedback and completed the quality review process.	Gudrun Haindlmaier (AIT) Ilias Papagiannopoulos (INCOMMON)
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ABBREVIATION

DMP	Data Management Plan
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
CS	Citizen Science
H&S	Healthy and Sustainable
PO	Project Objectives
WPs	Work Packages
CSLs	Citizen Science Labs
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
BCIs	Behavioral Change Interventions
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
ORE	Open Research Europe
CC	Creative Commons
ERI	European Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
DOIs	Digital Object Identifiers
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	1
2	DATA SUMMARY	2
2.1	Purpose of the data generation	2
2.2	Types and formats of data.....	4
2.3	Use of Existing Data.....	5
2.4	Data Utility	7
3	FAIR DATA	8
3.1	Making data FINDABLE, including provisions for metadata	8
3.2	Making data ACCESSIBLE	9
3.3	Making data INTEROPERABLE	10
3.4	Increase data RE-USE	11
4	ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	13
5	DATA SECURITY	14
5.1	Provisions for data security	14
5.2	Data Protocols	14
6	ETHICAL ASPECTS	15
6.1	Ethics on Data Management	15
6.2	Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation.....	15
6.3	Anonymization/pseudonymization applications.....	16
ANNEX 1	18

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	Overall SPOON project objectives (PO)	2
Table 2	Overview of potential resources for use of existing data	6
Table 3	Formats and tools of data files used in SPOON	10

1 INTRODUCTION

The global food system is currently under pressure from multiple, interconnected challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and unsustainable dietary patterns. These challenges demand an urgent transformation to prevent food insecurity and promote long-term sustainability. In response, the SPOON project proposes a paradigm shift by placing citizens at the core of this transformation through the use of Citizen Science (CS). By empowering individuals to contribute to research and data collection, SPOON aims to support healthier and more sustainable food choices across Europe.

To achieve this, the project adopts an interdisciplinary approach that integrates behavioural science, digital innovation, and data-driven interventions. This approach promotes ethical, transparent, and secure data sharing while actively engaging citizens in real-world food environments.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) contributes to SPOON's overarching objectives by providing a structured and responsible approach to managing research data across its entire lifecycle. It supports citizen engagement, facilitates behavioural change, and ensures the ethical and efficient use of data. The DMP is aligned with the principles of **Open Science** and complies with relevant EU regulations, particularly the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**.

To achieve these aims, SPOON follows the **FAIR principles** (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), ensuring that data collected, processed, and shared within the project is usable for both current and future research and policy efforts. The DMP also supports transparency and accountability in how data is accessed, stored, shared, and reused. The **SPOON Data Manager, Jurgen Vangeyte (EV ILVO)**, will oversee the implementation of data governance policies across the project.

The initial DMP is developed by **Month 6 (M6)** of the project, in May 2025. The DMP will be updated periodically based on project developments regarding the data management policies and ethical aspects by **M20**, July 2026, and finalized by **M38**, January 2028.

The document is structured to reflect the key components of effective data management. It begins with a Data Summary (**Section 2**), outlining the types, sources, formats, and intended uses of data collected. **Section 3** addresses how data will comply with FAIR principles. **Section 4** describes the allocation of resources dedicated to data management. **Section 5** focuses on data security measures, including protocols and safeguards, while **Section 6** outlines the ethical aspects, such as informed consent, anonymization, and legal compliance.

2 DATA SUMMARY

2.1 PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATION

The SPOON project aims to transform food systems, reshape the food value chain, foster data-driven decision-making, and engage citizens in changing their food consumption behavior and food environments. To achieve its aim, the project will pursue 5 detailed objectives (divided into two sets of main objectives) based on different target groups (See [Table 1](#)).

Table 1 Overall SPOON project objectives (PO)

Objective set #1: Using CS as a means Target groups: Policymakers, scientific community, businesses
PO1 More accurate & context-specific knowledge about local food environments available to researchers, policymakers and businesses
PO2 Increased capacity of policymakers in food, health, mobility and related sectors to make data-driven decisions that reduce food insecurity
PO3 Identified pathways for increased collaboration across sectors
Objective set #2: Using CS as an end Target group: Citizens
PO4 Increased agency of citizens & communities to change food consumption behaviour patterns and local food environments for less food insecurity
PO5 More citizens confident in sharing their personal data on food and other consumption behaviour

To achieve this, SPOON is divided into eight Work Packages (WPs), each with a specific role:

- **WP1 - Research on food system dynamics:** Understand challenges and ethics of collecting food-related data from citizens; overview of behavioral factors, methodologies, and interventions that impact European H&S food consumption.
- **WP2 - Development and deployment of digital tools and data management:** Analyze digital tools, develop and test the SPOON toolset, and create data governance framework. Test digital tools that help collect and analyze personal food data while protecting privacy and connect them to existing applications and platforms in the agri-food-value chain.
- **WP3 - Citizen Science Labs centralize framework, coordination and guidance:** Develop an effective and human-centered common framework for all Citizen Science Labs (CSLs). Map key stakeholders in the food systems and other relevant sectors, and activate them to enable consumer behavior changes.
- **WP4 - Citizen Science Labs & stakeholder engagement:** Engage citizens in CSLs to have a better understanding of challenges of sharing personal data, study food habits and help

transform the food systems by implementing the behavioral change interventions. Test and validate new solutions created in WP2.

- **WP5 - Impact evaluation and monitoring:** Provide a framework for impact evaluation and facilitate the implementation of monitoring activities within SPOON. To be specific, WP5 aims to measure the impact of CSLs and the SPOON tools. As well as improve the impact potential of CSLs.
- **WP6 - Exploitation, replication and upscaling:** Set-up and carry out an effective and ambitious Exploitation Plan, establish collaboration with sister projects. Ensure long-term use of SPOON results by creating business models and policy suggestions.
- **WP7 - Communication and dissemination:** Conduct targeted, effective, high-impact communication, engagement, and dissemination activities. Share knowledge and results to encourage adoption across Europe.
- **WP8 - Project Management:** Manage the project smoothly, ensuring all tasks are completed on time and meet quality standards. Manage project data in an effective and ethical way, and report on project performance regularly.

As of the current stage of the project, the following data-generating activities are foreseen across the work packages (WPs):

- **WP1** will involve activities such as a Systematic Literature Review, Focus Groups, and Surveys to explore citizens' food choices and motivations.
- **WP2** will generate data through a multi-media questionnaire generator as well as managed through a combination of toolsets, including a data wallet, DataU, and the DATALAKE infrastructure, focusing on data governance and citizen data control.
- **WP3** will conduct a Systematic Literature Review (using snowballing and desk research) and may include data derived from CSL experiences and relevant legacy datasets from previous projects.
- **WP4** will generate a wide range of data via CSLs and Citizen Science Projects, through real-time behavioral observation, workshops, behavioral change interventions, focus groups, interviews, app interactions, and environmental monitoring related to food environments and sustainability.
- **WP5** will collect both quantitative and qualitative data through literature reviews, partner contributions, surveys, and CSL activities, focusing on impact evaluation and monitoring.
- **WP6** will generate datasets and reports based on market trends, forecasts, and exploitation potential analysis.
- **WP7** will gather communication and engagement-related data, including website and platform analytics, social media statistics, workshops, newsletter, and event registration data.
- **WP8** will maintain a project database containing limited personal and professional information (e.g., names, roles, contact details) of project participants and stakeholders for project management purposes. This data will be stored in a structured format and securely hosted on internal MS Teams systems.

2.2 TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA

Due to the project's diverse objectives and activities, a variety of data types will be generated, collected, and stored throughout SPOON, requiring the use of different formats depending on their source and intended use.

The project is expected to generate the following main categories of data:

1. **Project Datasets** – structured datasets collected from surveys, tools, observational logs, and citizen interactions. **Various Types of Data**, including:
 - General research data, such as aggregated trends and behavioral patterns;
 - Personal data, including demographic characteristics, behavioural responses, and interaction logs;
 - Potentially sensitive data, e.g., health-related or food habit information gathered through surveys or app tools.
2. **Project Documentation and Reports** – internal and public-facing outputs, such as deliverables, meeting notes, technical documentation, and evaluation summaries.
3. **Digital Toolsets** – including the online **multi-media generator questionnaire**, **DataU**, **personal data wallet**, and the SPOON **DATALAKE**. The questionnaire may collect personal data such as name, age, gender, education, income, and geographical location, as well as content information. DataU does not store data but handles consent and stores it on the blockchain, ensuring GDPR compliance. The data wallet will collect and store personal data (e.g., questionnaire responses) with full transparency and individual control. The DATALAKE holds anonymized datasets, which will be open access.

In addition, the SPOON project will work with a wide range of research data formats, including:

- Quantitative data from experimental studies, structured surveys, and qualitative methods such as workshops, interviews, and focus groups;
- Data related to co-designed behavioral change interventions (BCIs);
- Comprehensive metadata describing dataset content, structure, and origin. Metadata will adhere to recognized standards such as Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) and Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT) to ensure clarity, interoperability, and reuse.

Many work packages will collect data directly through SPOON activities and Citizen Science Labs (CSLs), while some datasets may also be accessed via the SPOON DATALAKE and trusted partners such as SFC. Citizen Science (CS) data will be relevant to various food system actors, including retailers, HoReCa, food suppliers, and distributors.

The data collected in SPOON will be analyzed and presented in deliverables as defined in the Grant Agreement (see D8.1), to be uploaded on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal after internal review by project partners and coordinators (see D8.2 on quality and risk management).

General project activities will also generate photos, press articles, PowerPoint presentations or posters, and scientific publications (see WP7 deliverables).

A table summarizing available data collection information per WP is provided in **Annex 1**. This table will be reviewed and updated periodically to ensure completeness in the DMP. Examples of data in SPOON include survey results, interview recordings, and videos obtained with the involved parties' consent in focus groups.

- The format of the recordings: mp3, mp4.
- The format of the transcription: .txt, .docx, text, image, report format with summarized findings (e.g., interactive activity flipcharts/photographs with permission), and survey responses.
- The dataset format: CSV will be the main format, others include docx, .PDF, .txt, .docx, .xlsx, pptx, .jpg, .png, .xml, WEBM.

2.3 USE OF EXISTING DATA

We will reuse existing data in the SPOON project, primarily within WP1, WP3, WP4, and WP6. This reuse is key to ensuring methodological continuity, building on existing evidence, and supporting informed design and implementation of our interventions.

Internal SPOON Data Reuse: Data and insights generated in SPOON tasks will be reused across work packages. For instance:

- Outputs from WP1 T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3 (e.g., best practices, data-sharing barriers) will guide and benchmark the co-design process in WP4, T4.2.1.
- Participant data collected during recruitment activities in WP3, T3.4 (e.g., background, motivations, and commitments) will support the set-up of Citizen Science Platforms in WP4, T4.1.1.
- Training materials from WP3, T3.3 will inform data collection and handling protocols during CSL implementation in WP4.
- Insights and outcomes from WP4 CSLs and BCIs will feed into monitoring, evaluation, and exploitation efforts in WP6.

This internal reuse enables longitudinal perspectives on citizen behaviors, increases comparability across project phases, and ensures coherence between tasks and WPs.

Reuse of External Data Sources: In addition to internal project data, SPOON will leverage a range of existing external data sources to contextualize, inform, and benchmark key activities across WPs. These include:

- Scientific literature and grey literature, such as academic publications, policy papers, and reports, particularly for WP1's analysis of data-sharing barriers and best practices.
- Open-access data platforms and prior EU projects, such as EU 1.5° Lifestyles and PSLifestyle, which provide structured datasets and methodological insights for WP1 and WP4.
- Statistical databases and urban monitoring tools, relevant to WP4 for establishing local baselines or interpreting behavioural data in CSLs.
- Public-facing resources, such as stakeholder platforms and initiatives, used in WP6 to understand and position SPOON's value proposition.

A preliminary list of potential external data resources is included in **Table 2**. This list will be updated as the project evolves and new opportunities for data reuse emerge.

Table 2 Overview of potential resources for use of existing data

Name	Category
eu-citizen.science	Data Platform / Portal
CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service)	Data Platform / Portal
ISTAT for Italy	Data Platform / Portal
DESTATIS for Germany	Data Platform / Portal
City of Braunschweig statistics	Data Platform / Portal
de.statista.com	Data Platform / Portal
Stadsmonitor Flanders	Data Platform / Portal
Brugge in cijfers	Data Platform / Portal
Scienscano food data	Data Platform / Portal
Urban Food Policy Council of Thessaloniki	Tool / Initiative
Voedselploeg	Tool / Initiative
Foodsharing Braunschweig	Tool / Initiative
Food Policy Council Braunschweig	Tool / Initiative
Ei-meet	Project
Foodwinners project Brugge	Project
EU 1.5° Lifestyles	Project
PSLifestyle	Project

2.4 DATA UTILITY

Data collected in the SPOON project will be used by three main groups: **external end-users**, **the scientific community**, and **the consortium partners**. The end-users represent a diverse group, including food producers, food businesses, processors, retailers, start-ups, policymakers (from EU to local level), educational institutions, and consumers.

The core of SPOON's mission is to enable wider use of data and insights by external stakeholders to drive transformation in the European agri-food system. Project results aimed at these **end-users**, including insights, reports, and data tools, will be made publicly available through the project website. In parallel, WP7's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plans will outline targeted strategies to effectively engage these stakeholders.

The **scientific community** will benefit from open access to the SPOON digital toolset, public project deliverables, reports, and peer-reviewed publications. These materials will be published on the project website and relevant repositories, ensuring broad accessibility.

Within the **consortium**, the 16 partners have identified their data needs through the internal data assessment exercise, accessible via the Microsoft Teams SharePoint. While internal data sharing supports project operations and coordination, our broader focus remains on maximizing the utility of data for external users.

Lastly, we will collaborate with the **sister projects**, including FoodMission and other aligned initiatives that may emerge during the project lifecycle, to discuss possible joint communications for similar end-users. If the future collaboration extends to data sharing or data-related exchanges, the appropriate management measures and resulting approach will be put in place and updated in the next version of DMP.

3 FAIR DATA

All research outputs will be managed according to FAIR principles:

- **Findability** – Publicly available data will be assigned DOIs and indexed in trusted Open Access repositories.
- **Accessibility** – Data that do not compromise commercial and industrial interests will be made openly accessible.
- **Interoperability** – Data formats will be compatible with widely used research software.
- **Reusability** – SPOON datasets will be linked to European Research Infrastructures (ERI) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) where possible.

In the following section, we will provide details of how the SPOON project will manage its data according to FAIR principles. Note that we will link to a GDPR-compliant data collection tool called **SPOON DATALAKE** to store non-personal data and relevant research outputs via the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform or Zenodo. For further information, please refer to 2.2.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

To ensure the findability of data in line with the FAIR principles, all published outputs (including datasets) will be assigned **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)**. These globally unique and persistent identifiers facilitate the identification, citation, and retrieval of data. DOIs will be automatically provided for peer-reviewed publications and for reports and datasets deposited in **ORE** and/or **Zenodo**, the project's primary open-access repository.

Open Research Europe (ORE) is the European Commission's open-access publishing platform for scientific articles stemming from Horizon-funded research. It enables fast, transparent, and free-of-charge publishing, ensuring compliance with the EU's open science policies. **Zenodo** is a trusted and secure open-access repository supported by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). It is designed to help researchers, institutions, and projects openly share, preserve, and showcase research outputs such as data, software, and publications. Zenodo ensures data findability and accessibility, especially when institutional or domain-specific repositories are not available. Both platforms support open science and the long-term preservation of research outputs.

The metadata of deposited datasets will be made openly available under a **Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0)** or equivalent license unless legitimate interests or legal constraints apply. The metadata will be machine-actionable and include at minimum, the following information:

- Description of the dataset (title, author(s), abstracts, key words, date of deposit, and embargo if applicable);
- Horizon Europe or Euratom funding details (grant agreement number, acronym, and project name);
- Licensing terms;

- Persistent identifiers (DOIs) for datasets, publications, authors, and their affiliated organizations and grants, where possible.

Where relevant, metadata will also include persistent identifiers for related research outputs, including publications and datasets.

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

To align with SPOON's commitment to Open Science and in accordance with Horizon Europe's guidelines on FAIR data management, most data generated or used in the project will be made openly accessible **by default**, unless specific **sensitivity, confidentiality, legal, or ethical concerns** apply.

Datasets expected to be shared openly include:

- Aggregated and anonymized data presented on the project website and through the SPOON digital toolset;
- Information related to events and project activities (e.g., location, date, demonstration types, and involved stakeholders—with prior informed consent);
- Public project outputs, such as reports, deliverables, peer-reviewed articles, educational resources, dissemination materials, and capacity-building content;
- Research data from surveys, interviews, and digital tools—**following anonymization, ethical review, and appropriate embargo periods.**

Nevertheless, certain data and deliverables will remain closed due to their sensitive nature. This includes materials related to project management that are only relevant internally and intellectual property—**D2.1 and D2.2** (Specifications for the SPOON Digital Toolset v1 and v2) and **D8.3** (Intellectual Property Rights Management Plan), which contain confidential and technical content unsuitable for public sharing.

All accessible datasets will be stored in open and standardized formats to ensure broad usability. Users can open and work with the data using common tools to access these datasets. Please refer to **Table 3** for further detailed information about dataset formats and tools/platforms. Metadata will follow recognized standards like DataCite to ensure discoverability and proper referencing.

In cases where access is restricted due to legal, ethical, or contractual constraints, users can request access directly from the relevant data owner. Access may be granted under specific conditions, including prior consent from data providers and appropriate anonymization measures, ensuring compliance with GDPR and project-specific data governance protocols.

To ensure proper validation, dissemination of primary results, and implementation of ethical safeguards (e.g., data anonymization), some datasets will be made available only **after an embargo period**, typically following the end of the project. However, during the project, access to such data may be granted upon justified request, data sharing agreements, and under specific conditions.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Data produced in the project will use common formats and standards in order to be interoperable. For the processing and publishing of data files, **Table 3** below provides an overview of the formats applied across various data types within the project.

Table 3 Formats and tools of data files used in SPOON

Data Type	Format	Tools/software
Container	tar, gzip, ZIP	WinRAR, 7-Zip, GNU Tar
Databases	XML, CSV	MySQL Workbench, pgAdmin, Excel, Notepad++
Video	MP4, MPEG, AV1, MOV	VLC Media Player, QuickTime Player, FFmpeg
Audio	WAV, MP3	Audacity, Windows Media Player, iTunes
Statistics	Rdata (.rda)	RStudio
Image	PDF, PNG, GIF	Adobe Acrobat Reader, GIMP
Tabular data	CSV, TAB	Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets, Notepad++
Tex	XML, PDF/A, HTML	Notepad++, Sublime Text, Adobe Acrobat Reader
Metadata format	DataCite	DataCite Metadata Generator, DataCite Content Resolver

In addition to using interoperable file formats, the SPOON project will adopt the [DataCite Metadata Schema \(version 4.5\)](#) to ensure consistent and comprehensive metadata across all datasets. This metadata will include mandatory and recommended fields such as:

- **Identifier:** Digital Object Identifier (DOI) automatically assigned upon upload to platforms like Zenodo or ORE
- **Creator:** Individuals or institutions responsible for data creation
- **Title:** Descriptive name of the dataset
- **Publisher:** Entity responsible for distributing or archiving the dataset
- **Publication Year:** Year the dataset becomes publicly available
- **Subject:** Keywords or classification codes
- **Language:** ISO 639-1 language codes
- **Resource Type & Format:** Description and technical format (e.g., PDF, XML)
- **Rights:** Licensing information (e.g., CC BY 4.0)

- **Description:** Free-text field for technical or contextual information
- **Funding Reference:** Details of financial support for dataset creation

SPOON will implement a clear and structured naming convention to support consistent data organization and referencing. Dataset names will include concise qualifiers indicating the data collection method and version, where appropriate. Furthermore, datasets will contain qualified references to related datasets, publications, or documentation.

In addition to metadata standards, SPOON will use available domain standards and templates for data documentation and structuring, where relevant. Where no established standards exist, SPOON will develop internal templates to ensure consistency across datasets, aligned with best practices in the field.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Licensing. All deposited datasets will be made openly available via suitable repositories under the latest version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0), or equivalent. Metadata associated with deposited data will be made openly available under CC0 or an equivalent license, while safeguarding legitimate interests such as personal data protection or intellectual property constraints.

Re-use Pathways. The SPOON project is committed to enabling broad data re-use, particularly by **external stakeholders** such as the scientific community, policymakers, civil society, and future EU-funded initiatives. To facilitate this, open datasets will be deposited in trusted open research data repositories such as Zenodo and Open Research Europe (ORE), under FAIR principles.

In addition to open repositories, SPOON develops and employs a range of **internal digital environments and tools** to support project data workflows and internal reuse. These include: the SPOON digital toolset, Microsoft Teams SharePoint, Google Drive, Internal cloud environments, and other potential platforms. Collected data stored in the DATALAKE will be curated and shared as open research data through platforms such as ORE and/or Zenodo. All datasets will include rich metadata to ensure discoverability and enable reuse by both human users and machines.

These tools are co-designed with stakeholders and CSL users, and are continuously refined to support interoperability and scalability. Where appropriate, connections are developed via APIs to platforms such as Who's the Boss and DjustConnect, allowing for broader data integration across digital ecosystems.

Target Users and Re-use Scenarios. The openly shared datasets are expected to be reused by a range of stakeholders, including academic researchers, public authorities, civil society organizations, educational institutions, and SMEs working on food system transformation, behavior change, or citizen engagement. The datasets will support follow-up research,

replication of successful interventions, policy-making, comparative analysis, and broader educational and social innovation purposes.

Sensitive data will be treated in accordance with GDPR and relevant ethics approvals. Pseudonymization or full anonymization will be applied where needed, and no personal data will be shared without proper consent and safeguards. This ensures that all reuse complies with legal and ethical standards while maximizing value creation through open science.

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

FAIR data management in the SPOON project is under WP8: Project Management, led by the project coordinator, CSCP. The project management team will be responsible for the continuous monitoring of all data-related activities. Furthermore, they will supervise the smooth adaptation of the data management plan guidelines and practices within the project. Their observations and the feedback received from the partners will be the results for the upcoming DMP updates.

All costs related to FAIR data management that will occur during the project implementation will be covered by the project budget. For SPOON, at least seven scientific articles and papers can be expected as a result of the project. These will be published in fee-based, open-access scientific journals that follow the Gold OA model. A dedicated budget has been allocated to cover the associated publication fees.

In addition to publication costs, the project has allocated internal resources, including person-months and technical infrastructure, for the implementation of FAIR data practices. This includes the development, use, and maintenance of internal digital environments (such as Microsoft Teams SharePoint and cloud storage systems) and SPOON digital toolset.

Furthermore, budgeted resources support the co-design and deployment of digital tools for citizen science data collection, as well as engagement activities with citizen science lab (CSL) participants. Resources are also available to enable collaboration with sister projects and other external initiatives, particularly where shared infrastructures, data harmonization, or coordinated dissemination activities are involved.

Any other additional costs that may relate to data management will be discussed among consortium members. If deemed eligible according to the Grant Agreement, they will be included in the updates of the DMP and processed as material or personnel costs under WP8 Project Management.

5 DATA SECURITY

5.1 PROVISIONS FOR DATA SECURITY

Personal data collected from project activities will be securely stored by the project partner responsible for its collection. This data will not be shared with other partners unless a formal data-sharing agreement is in place or unless the data has been fully anonymized. If personal data sharing or transfer is required, informed consent will be obtained from the data owners before any sharing.

Anonymized personal data will be stored in the SPOON DATALAKE. The anonymization process includes the removal of direct identifiers (e.g., name, address, contact details), pseudonymization of participant IDs, and aggregation or generalization of sensitive variables where needed (see Section 6.3 for further information about anonymization and pseudonymization applications). The responsible project partners will carry out the anonymization before data is uploaded to the DATALAKE. This ensures that data is no longer attributable to individuals. It also enables the reuse of anonymized data by project partners, external researchers, tool developers, and food system actors for research and innovation.

Other project-related data, including documentation, reports, meeting records, and intermediate research outputs, will be stored both locally by the respective project partners and in a secure SharePoint environment provided by CSCP. Access to SharePoint is restricted to authorized consortium members, and daily backups are maintained to ensure data recovery.

Final research outputs and datasets will also be made available on the SPOON website, as well as deposited in open repositories such as Zenodo and Open Research Europe (ORE). All data stored in SharePoint, DATALAKE, and Zenodo/ORE will be securely maintained with regular backups to ensure long-term preservation and integrity.

5.2 DATA PROTOCOLS

Data Protocols for surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and workshops will be developed by the partner organizations in charge of the tasks where this work takes place. After the data protocols are developed, they will be added to the DMP as appendices. The internal ethical working group will assess them for compliance with the GDPR and other regulations.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICS ON DATA MANAGEMENT

The data management in SPOON will fully comply with the regulations set out in Article 14 of the Grant Agreement, which states that the beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:

- Ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity) and,
- Applicable EU, international, and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, and its Supplementary Protocols.

This includes following the principles set out in the European Charter for Researchers and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, as well as ensuring full compliance with the GDPR.

Humans: The project will carry out qualitative-quantitative behavioral studies and interventions with participants by involving the CSLs and Living Labs through desk research, focus groups, surveys, case studies, and experiments. Furthermore, children/minors are not within the study scope, but vulnerable adults may participate, provided valid informed consent is obtained. All activities involving human participants will be subject to ethical review, and where necessary, **ethical approval** will be obtained from the relevant institutional or national ethics committees.

Personal Data: The project will collect various personal data to analyze consumer behavior. The undertaken activities may involve the profiling of people. Furthermore, these data may include potentially sensitive categories such as dietary habits, social norms, and lifestyle preferences to support research activities.

Artificial Intelligence: The data analysis will be supported by open-source artificial intelligence (AI) tools, which will be selected during the data analysis phase by the CSL coordinators together with project partners. To prepare for this, we have shared the document “**Questions AI Guidelines – template v8**” with all partners to collect their input on possible AI tools, methods, and ethical considerations. The final choice of tools will take into account relevance to the research goals, alignment with project data standards, and compliance with ethical and legal requirements.

6.2 INFORMED CONSENT FOR DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

All data collected within the SPOON project is obtained with the explicit consent of participants, in full compliance with GDPR regulations and MyData principles. All data collection activities involving personal data will strictly follow the GDPR and national data

protection laws. Data minimization and purpose limitation will be guiding principles, only the data necessary for achieving the specific research objectives will be collected and processed.

Prior to each activity and the use of any tool that collects research data, informed consent forms will be provided to all participants. This ensures that individuals are fully aware of how their data will be used and can make informed decisions regarding their participation. (Related task: T2.3)

Whenever a citizen chooses to share personal data with an application, this process is managed through DATAU, allowing individuals to grant explicit consent for data sharing under specific conditions or within a defined timeframe. The personal DATAU dashboard provides an overview of all previously given consents, enabling individuals to manage their permissions and exercise their GDPR rights effectively.

For long-term data preservation, the DATALAKE could serve as a secure repository for anonymized datasets derived from various applications connected to the SPOON digital architecture. Each application must obtain explicit consent from participants before anonymizing their data for inclusion in publicly available datasets. The anonymized data stored in the DATALAKE may continue to be used beyond the project's duration, for example, to train AI algorithms and develop new services.

Furthermore, the evaluation of the SPOON toolset's socio-ecological, technological, and economic dimensions will be conducted through dedicated online workshops, applying the Fair Consumption Space framework (WP5).

6.3 ANONYMIZATION/PSEUDONYMIZATION APPLICATIONS

Given that the SPOON project involves consumer-related data, particular attention will be paid to the protection of personal information. Project partners will apply anonymization and pseudonymization techniques where relevant, especially in cases where quantitative or qualitative data may involve directly or indirectly identifiable information. As mentioned in Section 5.1, the responsible project partners have to carry out the anonymization before data is uploaded to the DATALAKE or shared with external stakeholders.

For **quantitative data**, directly identifying elements such as names, email addresses, and IP addresses will be removed. Where indirect identifiers exist, generalization techniques such as k-anonymity will be considered (with k=5 as a reference), provided that data utility can be maintained.

For **qualitative data**, identifiable content will be replaced or masked using square brackets (e.g., [participant], [city], [organization]). Due to the rich and contextual nature of such data, partners will take extra care to ensure individuals cannot be re-identified, even when combining data points.

The application of anonymization or pseudonymization will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, depending on the nature of the dataset and the research need. If data cannot be sufficiently anonymized without losing meaning, stricter access limitations and local storage (without sharing) may be applied, in line with data protection regulations and the project's ethical principles.

Note: Only personal data that has been properly anonymized or pseudonymized may be shared with other partners or made publicly available.

ANNEX 1

Overview of data collection in SPOON

WP	Type of Data	Collection Method	Personal Data Involved	Data Format	Estimated Volume	Storage Platforms	Leading Partner
WP1	Primary Data (Qualitative & Quantitative), Secondary Data (Qualitative)	Focus Group, Systematic Literature Review, Survey	Yes	Text, reports, survey responses, images, audio files, and video files	50-100 papers, Literature Review Output: 30–50 pages (~200 KB to 1 MB, digital text); Focus Group Transcripts: 24–60 pages total (~1–2 MB, unstructured text); Reporting Templates: 30 pages (~300–500 KB, structured summaries); The rest is to be decided.	Most of the output will be stored in MS Teams, the CSCP internal cloud, and AI-software Rayyan, the survey data storage platform is to be decided.	EV ILVO
WP2	Quantitative Data, Qualitative Data, Personal Data, CSL Data	Questionnaire through the toolset	Yes	structured, non-structured data, text	Depends on the CSLs, to be decided	Data Wallet	JIBE
WP3	Qualitative Data, Literature & Reports (Secondary Data)	Systematic Literature Review (using snowballing and desk research), data derived from CSL experiences, and relevant legacy datasets from previous projects	Yes	Structured data, Semi-structured data, unstructured data, text,	Literature review: 5-10 documents; previous projects: 3-5 reports; data derived from CSLs depends on CSLs.	Microsoft Teams, Google Sheets in Drive	SFC

WP4	Observational Data, Experimental Data, Derived/Compiled Data	Field observation (CSLs, CSPs), SPOON toolset, Multimedia recordings (photos, videos, audio), Workshops, Surveys & self-reported tools (e.g., food diaries), Pre/post intervention studies, Purchase tracking (e.g., receipts), App usage analytics (nudges, gamification), Environmental scanning, Stakeholder analysis, Comparative case reviews	Yes	text, images, audio files, video files, reports, survey responses	Stakeholder engagement data: ~50MB per survey batch (raw + processed data); Multimedia recordings (meetings, events, pilots): ~200MB–1GB per major event (~5GB overall); Pilot reports and behavioral analyses: ~20MB per report (~500MB overall). Overall estimated size: ~6–10GB over the project duration, depending on multimedia content.	MS Teams and the CSCPC internal cloud	CSCP
WP5	Quantitative and qualitative data	Literature Review, CSLs and Partners, Survey	No	Anonymized data	To be decided	MS teams folder (Sharepoint) and the DataLake	AIT
WP6	Reports/Datasets	Market data, trends and forecasts	No	Reports/Datasets	To be decided	MS Teams	PNO
WP7	Communication & Engagement	Website & platform analytics	Yes	Structured data, Unstructured data	To be decided	Wordpress, ICONS cloud	ICONs

	Data; Website Analytics; Personal Data (event participants)	(e.g., MATOMO, Talkwalker); Social media analytics (Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube; Newsletter subscriptions; Landing page and event registrations; Workshop/webinar registration forms					
WP8	Name and surname, country, position or role in the organisation/ project, email, work telephone number	Database	Yes	Structured data	Less than 1MB	MS Teams	CSCP

CONSORTIUM

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